

On the Knee-point of Cross-Ply Composite

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ABSTRACT

The present paper is to give a supplementary knowledge to the well-known S.W. Tsai's concept of the 'knee-point' appearing in the stress-strain diagram of a cross-ply composite under uniaxial tension. While Tsai had avoided to do, the behavior immediately after the knee-point is examined in detail, and also the behavior in the case of unloading is predicted. Two material properties were assumed; ductile and brittle. When ductile matrix is assumed, the stress-strain diagram is almost the same as that of Tsai, although, microscopically, it takes a staggered path. In case of brittle matrix, the result differs notably from that of Tsai. The present theory predicts that the unloading path is parallel to the initial loading path.

INTRODUCTION

The strength of a glass/epoxy cross-ply under uniaxial tension has been analysed by S.W. Tsai et al. (1). The stress-strain diagram consists of two straight lines; the intersection was called by Tsai the 'knee-point'. The point represents the failure of the inner layer. In his analysis, the concept of ductile or brittle material properties does not enter. He avoided to examine the post-failure behavior. His method is as follows; the knee-point obtained; independently the final fracture point determined; a straight line drawn to connect the two points.

The present paper is to give a supplementary knowledge to Tsai's theory. A method will be presented to analyse the post-failure behaviors. To this effect, two idealized material properties are assumed; ductile and brittle. Successive failure loads and the post-failure behaviors will be analysed. The case of unloading will also be discussed.

BASIC EQUATIONS FOR GENERAL LAMINATED COMPOSITES

The basic equations will be first given here for general symmetric FRP laminated plates subjected to combined in-plane loads. They have been published by one of the authors in (2) to (6), and by the authors in (7) and (8).

The total thickness of the plate is denoted by t , and N is the number of constituent layers. Layer number is indicated by the superscript (i) . The layer

thickness is denoted by $t^{(i)}$, and its thickness ratio by $h^{(i)} = t^{(i)}/t$. Fig.1 defines the positive sense of stresses in a constituent layer. (x,y) are the reference coordinates, $\theta^{(i)}$ is the lamination angle measured from the x-axis.

$(L^{(i)}, T^{(i)})$ are the layer coordinates where $L^{(i)}$ is the longitudinal axis parallel to the fiber direction and $T^{(i)}$ is the transverse axis perpendicular to $L^{(i)}$. For simplicity, the vectors $\{\sigma_x^{(i)}, \sigma_y^{(i)}, \tau_{xy}^{(i)}\}$, $\{\sigma_L^{(i)}, \sigma_T^{(i)}, \tau_{LT}^{(i)}\}$, etc. are expressed as $\{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\}$, $\{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\}$, etc. by writing the first element only. The first, the second, and the third elements are to carry the subscripts x,y,xy or L,T,LT in this order. The letter σ denotes the stress, and ϵ the strain. When a letter does not carry the superscript (i) , it means the quantity associated with the whole thickness. $\{ \}$ denotes the column matrix, $[\]$ the rectangular matrix, $[\]^T$ the transpose. The stresses and strains are decomposed into two parts: The one, due to the applied loads, and the other, due to the thermal stresses.

Fig. 1. Definition of stresses in a constituent layer.

Total stresses and strains are

$$\{\epsilon_L^{(i)}\} = \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} + \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} \quad (1) \quad \{\epsilon_x\} = \{\epsilon_x^{(i)}\} = \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} + \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} \quad (2)$$

$$\{\sigma_L^{(i)}\} = \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} + \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} \quad (3) \quad \{\sigma_x^{(i)}\} = \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} + \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} \quad (4)$$

$$\{\sigma_x\} = \{\bar{\sigma}_x\} = \sum_{i=1}^N h^{(i)} \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} \quad (5)$$

Quantities due to applied loads are

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} = [A^{(i)}] \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} \quad (6) \quad \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} = [B^{(i)}]^T \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} \quad (7)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = [B^{(i)}] \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} \quad (8) \quad \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} = [A^{(i)}]^T \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} \quad (9)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = [D^{(i)}] \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} + \{p^{(i)}\} \quad (10) \quad \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = [H^{(i)}] \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} + \{p^{(i)}\} \quad (11)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} = [C^{(i)}] \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} + [A^{(i)}]^T \{p^{(i)}\} \quad (12)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_x\} = [f] \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} + \{Q\} \quad (13) \quad \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} = [F] (\{\sigma_x\} - \{Q\}) \quad (14)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = [K^{(i)}] (\{\sigma_x\} - \{Q\}) + \{p^{(i)}\} \quad (15) \quad \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} = [V^{(i)}] (\{\sigma_x\} - \{Q\}) \quad (16)$$

where

$$l^{(i)} = \cos \theta^{(i)}, \quad m^{(i)} = \sin \theta^{(i)} \quad (17)$$

$$[A^{(i)}] = \begin{bmatrix} l^{(i)2} & m^{(i)2} & -2l^{(i)}m^{(i)} \\ m^{(i)2} & l^{(i)2} & 2l^{(i)}m^{(i)} \\ 2l^{(i)}m^{(i)} & -2l^{(i)}m^{(i)} & l^{(i)2} - m^{(i)2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$[B^{(i)}] = \begin{bmatrix} l^{(i)2} & m^{(i)2} & -2l^{(i)}m^{(i)} \\ m^{(i)2} & l^{(i)2} & 2l^{(i)}m^{(i)} \\ l^{(i)}m^{(i)} & -l^{(i)}m^{(i)} & l^{(i)2} - m^{(i)2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$[D^{(i)}] = \begin{bmatrix} E_L^{(i)} & \nu_L^{(i)} E_T^{(i)} & 0 \\ \nu_T^{(i)} E_L^{(i)} & E_T^{(i)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{LT}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$E_L^{(i)} = E_L^{(i)} / (1 - \nu_L^{(i)} \nu_T^{(i)}), \quad E_T^{(i)} = E_T^{(i)} / (1 - \nu_L^{(i)} \nu_T^{(i)}), \quad \nu_T^{(i)} E_L^{(i)} = \nu_L^{(i)} E_T^{(i)} \quad (21)$$

$$[H^{(i)}] = [D^{(i)}][A^{(i)}] \quad (22) \quad [C^{(i)}] = [A^{(i)}]^T [H^{(i)}] \quad (23)$$

$$[f] = \sum_{i=1}^N h^{(i)} [C^{(i)}] \quad (24) \quad [F] = [f]^{-1} \quad (25)$$

$$[K^{(i)}] = [H^{(i)}][F] \quad (26) \quad [\nabla^{(i)}] = [A^{(i)}][F] \quad (27)$$

$$\{p^{(i)}\} = [L^{(i)}]\{F_L^{(i)}\} \quad (28)$$

$$[L^{(i)}] = \begin{bmatrix} L_1^{(i)} & L_2^{(i)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & L_3^{(i)} & L_4^{(i)} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & L_5^{(i)} & L_6^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{where } L_k^{(i)} = 1 \text{ or } 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\{F_L^{(i)}\} = [F_{L_t}^{(i)}, F_{L_c}^{(i)}, F_{T_t}^{(i)}, F_{T_c}^{(i)}, +F_{L_T}^{(i)}, -F_{L_T}^{(i)}]^T \quad (30)$$

$$\{Q\} = \sum_{i=1}^N h^{(i)} [A^{(i)}]^T \{p^{(i)}\} \quad (31)$$

In eqs. (6) to (9), $[A^{(i)}]$ and $[B^{(i)}]$ are the coefficients of coordinate transformation. In eq. (10), $[D^{(i)}]$ is the elastic moduli for the plane stress problem. $\{p^{(i)}\}$ in eq. (10) is the plastic stress for the case of ductile material. In eq. (30), F_{L_t} , F_{L_c} , and F_{L_T} denote the critical values of σ_L , σ_T and τ_{LT} respectively, which represent the failure stresses. F_{L_t} is the failure stress F_L in tension, F_{L_c} the failure stress F_L in compression. The same is meant by F_{T_t} and F_{T_c} . $+F_{L_T}$ is the positive shear and $-F_{L_T}$ the negative shear. In the elastic region, $L_k^{(i)}$ of eq. (29) are all zero. When a failure represented by some component of eq. (30) occurred, the corresponding $L_k^{(i)}$ is set to be unity. As seen from eq. (31), $\{Q\}$ is the term related to the plastic stress.

In the case of brittle material, $\{p^{(i)}\}$ and $\{Q\}$ are null.

Due to the heat treatment during the manufacturing process, the thermal stresses are inherent in the initial unloaded specimens. Quantities due to thermal stresses are

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} = [A^{(i)}]\{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} \quad (32) \quad \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} = [B^{(i)}]^T \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} \quad (33)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = [B^{(i)}]\{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} \quad (34) \quad \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} = [A^{(i)}]^T \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} \quad (35)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = [D^{(i)}](\{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} - \{\alpha_L^{(i)}\} \Delta T) \quad (36) \quad \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = [H^{(i)}]\{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} - \{G^{(i)}\} \Delta T \quad (37)$$

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)}\} = [C^{(i)}]\{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} - [A^{(i)}]^T \{G^{(i)}\} \Delta T \quad (38)$$

where

$$\{\alpha_L^{(i)}\} = [\alpha_L^{(i)}, \alpha_T^{(i)}, 0]^T \quad (39) \quad \{G^{(i)}\} = [D^{(i)}]\{\alpha_L^{(i)}\} \quad (40)$$

α_L and α_T are the coefficients of thermal expansion in L and T directions, respectively. ΔT is the temperature difference due to the heat treatment. $\{\alpha_L^{(i)}\} \Delta T$ represents the free thermal expansion.

The thermal stresses are self-equilibrating, therefore $\{\bar{\sigma}_x\} = 0$. Hence it follows:

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} = \{\bar{\epsilon}_x^{(i)}\} = [F]\{J\} \Delta T \quad (41) \quad \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(i)}\} = ([K^{(i)}]\{J\} - \{G^{(i)}\}) \Delta T \quad (42)$$

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(i)}\} = [\nabla^{(i)}]\{J\} \Delta T \quad (43)$$

where

$$\{J\} = \sum_{i=1}^N h^{(i)} [A^{(i)}]^T \{G^{(i)}\} \quad (44)$$

All the computation was performed at Computer Center of Kyushu University.

CROSS-PLY: DUCTILE CASE

The three-layers cross-ply treated by Tsai is illustrated in Fig. 2a. The external load is the uni-axial tension $N_x = \sigma_x \cdot t$. The two outer layers are of equal thicknesses. For simplicity of calculation, the actual cross-ply is decomposed into equivalent two-layers cross-ply as shown in Fig. 2b. The two outer layers of (a) are inclusively expressed as layer 1 in (b), and the inner layer of (a) is layer 2 in (b). In this case, the shear deformation δ_{LT} does not occur. Hence, in the matrix calculation, the terms corresponding to δ_{LT} may be dropped.

The following numerical values of Tsai (1) for a glass/epoxy composite are used: $h^{(1)} = 1/6$, $h^{(2)} = 5/6$, $\theta^{(1)} = 0^\circ$, $\theta^{(2)} = 90^\circ$, $E_L = 7.8 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} = 53.78 \text{ GPa}$, $E_T = 2.6 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} = 17.93 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{LT} = 1.25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} = 8.618 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_L = 0.25$, $F_{LT} = -F_{Lc} = 150 \text{ ksi} = 1.034 \text{ GPa}$, $F_{Tt} = 4 \text{ ksi} = 27.58 \text{ MPa}$, $F_{Tc} = -20 \text{ ksi} = -137.9 \text{ MPa}$, $F_{LT} = 6 \text{ ksi} = 41.37 \text{ MPa}$, $\alpha_L = 3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{F} = 6.300 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/K}$, $\alpha_T = 11.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{F} = 20.52 \times 10^{-6} \text{ 1/K}$, $\Delta T = -200^\circ\text{F} = -111.1 \text{ K}$.

(a) Actual cross-ply

(b) Equivalent decomposition

Fig. 2. Cross-ply

Initial State At Room Temperature

In the curing stage at high temperature, the total strain is $\{\epsilon_x\} = 0$. At room temperature, if each layer was independent, the free thermal contractions are $\alpha_L^{(1)} \Delta T = \alpha_L^{(2)} \Delta T = -0.00070$, $\alpha_T^{(1)} \Delta T = \alpha_T^{(2)} \Delta T = -0.00280$. Since two layers are bonded together, the thermal stresses and strains occur. From eqs. (41) and (42),

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_x^{(1)} = \bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)} &= -48.99 \text{ MPa}, & \bar{\sigma}_y^{(1)} = \bar{\sigma}_T^{(1)} &= 21.96 \text{ MPa}, \\ \bar{\sigma}_x^{(2)} = \bar{\sigma}_T^{(2)} &= 9.80 \text{ MPa}, & \bar{\sigma}_y^{(2)} = \bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)} &= -4.39 \text{ MPa}, \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{x0} \equiv \bar{\epsilon}_x &= -0.00171, & \bar{\epsilon}_{y0} \equiv \bar{\epsilon}_y &= -0.00083. \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

The quantities due to applied load are null, i.e., $\{\sigma_x^{(i)}\} = \{\epsilon_x^{(i)}\} = 0$. The elastic moduli are

$$[\mathcal{D}^{(1)}] = [\mathcal{D}^{(2)}] = \begin{bmatrix} E_L' & \nu_L E_T' \\ \nu_L E_T' & E_T' \end{bmatrix} \tag{46}$$

The First Failure Load

As will be seen in the subsequent parts, in order to analyse the post-failure behavior, it is advantageous to use the maximum stress theory as the failure criterion. The criterion immediately follows from eqs. (3) and (15), by substituting the critical values $\{F_L^{(i)}\}$ in place of $\{\sigma_L^{(i)}\}$. Since there is no plastic stress as yet, $\{p^{(i)}\} = 0$. The applied load is σ_x only, thus $\sigma_y = \tau_{xy} = 0$. The failure criterion for the first failure is written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_L^{(1)} \text{ mode} : \quad \sigma_x &= (F_L^{(1)} - \bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}) / K_{11}^{(1)}, & F_L^{(1)} &= F_{Lt} \text{ or } F_{Lc} \\ F_T^{(1)} \text{ mode} : \quad \sigma_x &= (F_T^{(1)} - \bar{\sigma}_T^{(1)}) / K_{21}^{(1)}, & F_T^{(1)} &= F_{Tt} \text{ or } F_{Tc} \\ F_L^{(2)} \text{ mode} : \quad \sigma_x &= (F_L^{(2)} - \bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}) / K_{11}^{(2)}, & F_L^{(2)} &= F_{Lt} \text{ or } F_{Lc} \\ F_T^{(2)} \text{ mode} : \quad \sigma_x &= (F_T^{(2)} - \bar{\sigma}_T^{(2)}) / K_{21}^{(2)}, & F_T^{(2)} &= F_{Tt} \text{ or } F_{Tc} \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

The minimum value obtained from eq. (47) is $\sigma_x = 23.85$ MPa in $F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}$ failure mode, which is almost the same, in this example, as that of Tsai. The $F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}$ is the failure in layer 2 due to tension in the direction transverse to fibers.

To the instant of failure, the following values are given:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= [K^{(1)}]\{\sigma_x\} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.272 & -0.1193 \\ 0.1193 & 0.3638 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 23.85 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 54.20 \\ 2.84 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= [K^{(2)}]\{\sigma_x\} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.02386 & 1.1272 \\ 0.7455 & 0.02386 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 23.85 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.57 \\ 17.78 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} &= [F]\{\sigma_x\} = \begin{bmatrix} 4.170 & -0.3909 \\ -0.3909 & 2.085 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 23.85 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \times 10^{-5} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.000995 \\ -0.000093 \end{Bmatrix} \\
 \{\sigma_x^{(1)}\} &= \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(1)}\} + \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(1)}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} 54.20 \\ 2.84 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} -48.99 \\ 21.96 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 5.21 \\ 24.81 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\sigma_x^{(2)}\} &= \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(2)}\} + \{\bar{\sigma}_x^{(2)}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} 17.78 \\ -0.57 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 9.80 \\ -4.39 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 27.58 \\ -4.96 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\epsilon_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} &= \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.000995 \\ -0.000093 \end{Bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

where, in the stress-strain diagram, the abscissa is taken as $\{\epsilon_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\}$. When the load σ_x is null, $\{\epsilon_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} = \{0\}$.

Post-Failure Behavior After The First Failure

The idea to use the maximum stress theory has been first proposed by K. Kawata (9). Discussions have been exchanged between Kawata and one of the authors to improve the concept about angle-ply under biaxial tension. Ductile cases have been investigated by one of the authors (3), (4) and by the authors (7), (8).

In the present paper, two idealized material properties, ductile and brittle, are assumed as shown in Fig. 3. The brittle case will be discussed later under the heading mentioned. Otherwise, the ductile case is concerned.

Due to $F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}$ failure, the elastic moduli of layer 2 change, i.e.,

$$[D^{(2)}] = \begin{bmatrix} E_L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{49}$$

The stress-strain relations for layer 2 are written from eq. (10) as follows:

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} = [D^{(2)}]\{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(2)}\} + \{\sigma_{F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}}\} \tag{50}$$

where the last term means the plastic stress of ductile material.

Due to the change of the stiffness of layer 2, rearrangement of stresses occurs at the same load.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= [K^{(1)}](\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{5}{6}\{F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}\}) = \begin{Bmatrix} 5.21 \\ 0.41 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= [K^{(2)}](\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{5}{6}\{F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}\}) + \{\sigma_{F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.08 \\ 27.58 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} &= [F](\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{5}{6}\{F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}\}) = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.000095 \\ -0.000002 \end{Bmatrix} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= ([K^{(1)}]\{J\} - \{G^{(1)}\})\Delta T = \begin{Bmatrix} 26.55 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= ([K^{(2)}]\{J\} - \{G^{(2)}\})\Delta T = \begin{Bmatrix} -5.31 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} &= [F]\{J\}\Delta T = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.000823 \\ -0.000799 \end{Bmatrix} \\
 \{\epsilon_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} &= \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} + \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.000985 \\ -0.000027 \end{Bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

In eqs. (51.4-5), we note that the thermal stresses were released in the x-direction. As in (51.6), the thermal strains also change.

At $\epsilon_x - \epsilon_{x_0} = 0.000985$, the plastic flow comes to cease, and it is another equilibrium point under the same load. Now the load can be increased until the second failure.

The Second Failure Load

Since the plastic stress $F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)}$ exists, $\{p^{(1)}\}$ and $\{Q\}$ in eq. (15) now take non-zero values. It is found that the $F_{T\epsilon}^{(1)}$ failure of layer 1 gives the minimum σ_x . Thus, from eqs. (3) and (15), the failure criterion becomes

$$K_{21}^{(1)}\sigma_x = F_{T\epsilon}^{(1)} - \bar{\sigma}_T^{(1)} + K_{21}^{(1)}Q_1 + K_{22}^{(1)}Q_2 = F_{T\epsilon}^{(1)} - \bar{\sigma}_T^{(1)} + \frac{5}{6}K_{21}^{(1)}F_{T\epsilon}^{(2)} : F_{T\epsilon}^{(1)} \text{ mode} \tag{52}$$

from which, the second failure load is found to be $\sigma_x=25.17$ MPa.

Similar to eq. (51), the stresses and strains at this instant are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= [K^{(1)}] (\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{5}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\}) = \{13.13\} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= [K^{(2)}] (\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{5}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\}) + \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\} = \{-0.21\} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} &= [F] (\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{5}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\}) = \{0.000239\} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= ([K^{(1)}] \{J\} - \{G^{(1)}\}) \Delta T = \{26.55\} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= ([K^{(2)}] \{J\} - \{G^{(2)}\}) \Delta T = \{-5.31\} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} &= [F] \{J\} \Delta T = \{-0.000823\} \\
 \{\epsilon_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} &= \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} + \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} = \{0.001129\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

Post-Failure Behavior After The Second Failure

Due to the failure of layer 1, the elastic moduli are changed as follows:

$$[\bar{D}^{(1)}] = [\bar{D}^{(2)}] = \begin{bmatrix} E_L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{54}$$

The stress-strain relations are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= [\bar{D}^{(1)}] \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(1)}\} + \{F_{Tt}^{(1)}\} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= [\bar{D}^{(2)}] \{\bar{\epsilon}_L^{(2)}\} + \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

Due to $F_{Tt}^{(1)}$ failure, the new plastic flow occurs at the same load, accompanying rearrangement of stresses. The flow comes to a settling point. The stresses and strains associated with this point are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= [K^{(1)}] (\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{1}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(1)}\} - \frac{5}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\}) + \{F_{Tt}^{(1)}\} = \{13.13\} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= [K^{(2)}] (\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{1}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(1)}\} - \frac{5}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\}) + \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\} = \{-5.52\} \text{ MPa} \\
 \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} &= [F] (\{\sigma_x\} - \frac{1}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(1)}\} - \frac{5}{6} \{F_{Tt}^{(2)}\}) = \{-0.000103\} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(1)}\} &= ([K^{(1)}] \{J\} - \{G^{(1)}\}) \Delta T = \{0\} \\
 \{\bar{\sigma}_L^{(2)}\} &= ([K^{(2)}] \{J\} - \{G^{(2)}\}) \Delta T = \{0\} \\
 \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} &= [F] \{J\} \Delta T = \{-0.000700\} \\
 \{\epsilon_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} &= \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} + \{\bar{\epsilon}_x\} - \{\epsilon_{x_0}\} = \{0.001257\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

Eqs. (56.4-5) indicate that the thermal stresses are now completely released due to $F_{Tt}^{(1)}$ and $F_{Tt}^{(2)}$ failures. Eq. (56.6) indicates that the thermal strains are equal to the free thermal contractions $\alpha_L \Delta T = -0.0007$. From eq. (56.7), the abscissa of the settling point in the stress-strain diagram is $\epsilon_x - \epsilon_{x_0} = 0.001257$. After reaching the settling point, the load can be increased again.

The Final Fracture Load

Explanation may be made by using matrix equations, but an elementary explanation will be more adequate. In the initial state, the composite is statically indeterminate. As one failure mode occurs, the degree of statical indeterminacy is reduced by one. At the final state, the composite becomes statically determinate. Thus, the final fracture point is determined from the following simple equations.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{\epsilon}_x &= \bar{\sigma}_x^{(1)} / E_L = F_{Lt}^{(1)} / E_L = 0.019230 \\
 \sigma_x &= \bar{\sigma}_x = \frac{1}{6} F_{Lt}^{(1)} + \frac{5}{6} F_{Tt}^{(2)} = 195.35 \text{ MPa} \\
 \epsilon_x - \epsilon_{x_0} &= \bar{\epsilon}_x + \bar{\epsilon}_x - \epsilon_{x_0} = 0.019230 - 0.000700 + 0.001713 = 0.020244
 \end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

Fig. 4. The stress-strain diagram of a glass/epoxy cross-ply composite, $h^{(1)}=1/6$, $h^{(2)}=5/6$.

Fig. 5. Expanded view around the knee-point for the ductile case.

Summary Of Ductile Case

The previous results are illustrated in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The solid line for the ductile case of Fig. 4 is almost the same as that of Tsai. Microscopically, however, the results of the present second approximation theory give the staggered path immediately after the knee-point which is the first corner noted by $F_{Tt}^{(2)}$ in Fig. 5. The concept of ductile or brittle material does not enter in the first approximation theory of Tsai. The present second approximation theory can state that Tsai's theory approximately gives the behavior of the ductile material. One of the significant implications of the present theory is the possibility of $F_{Tt}^{(1)}$ failure in layer 1. The explanation is as follows: When layer 1 is pulled in the x-direction, it tends to contract in the y-direction due to the effect of Poisson's ratio. However, the fibers of layer 2 are still healthy in the y-direction. This prevents the contraction of layer 1, producing tension in the y-direction. The tension reaches the critical value, hence $F_{Tt}^{(1)}$ failure.

CROSS-PLY COMPOSITE: BRITTLE CASE

The brittle property is illustrated in Fig. 3. Once the stress reached the critical value, cracks are produced. The stress falls to zero and the material can no more bear the increasing load.

In the case of brittle material, all the terms representing the plastic stress, such as $\{p^{(1)}\}$ and $\{Q\}$, are dropped in the previous equations. Calculations similar to the ductile case are performed. The results are illustrated in Fig. 4 by the dotted line.

The significant difference from the ductile case is the notable slip immediately after the initial failure. At the initial failure, $F_{Tt}^{(1)}$ and $F_{Tt}^{(2)}$ modes occur simultaneously. This slip is due to crack, not due to plastic flow. The loading path after the initial failure is exactly parallel to the ductile path. The final fracture occurs exactly at the same $\epsilon_x - \epsilon_{x0}$ as that point of the ductile case. When the dotted inclined line is extended to intersect the abscissa, the intersecting point does not coincide with the origin. This is because that, after $F_{Tt}^{(1)}$ and $F_{Tt}^{(2)}$ failure, the thermal stresses are completely released. The cross-ply becomes effectively longer. If the effects of thermal stresses are neglected from the theory, the intersecting point coincides with the origin.

UNLOADING

When the load exceeded the initial failure point and then unloaded, it takes the path as shown in Fig. 6. Both paths for ductile and brittle cases are exactly parallel to the initial elastic path.

The ductile case is explained first. On the loading path, $[D^{(1)}]$ and $[D^{(2)}]$ are of the values of eq. (54). However, noting the characteristics of Fig. 3a, it will be most natural to assume that $[D^{(1)}]$ regain the elastic property. Thus, when unloading, $[D^{(1)}]$ and $[D^{(2)}]$ assume the elastic values of eq. (46). Taking the initial point at $\sigma_x = 100$ MPa, similar calculation as before is performed by putting the increment of load as $\Delta\sigma_x = -100$ MPa. Caution should be paid that, at $\sigma_x = 100$ MPa, the thermal stresses have been released already, and hence the thermal stress terms should be dropped in the unloading calculation.

Now for the brittle case. K. Kawata (9) has proposed the concept of the open crack case and the close crack case, and the stability criterion of failure. Consider two bricks.

When they are separated, there is no resistance. When they are compressed each other, the closed crack can carry load. When unloading, layer 1 and 2 are in the close crack case. Hence, in this case as well, $[D^{(1)}]$ regain the elastic values. The method of calculation is analogous to the ductile case.

Fig. 6. Unloading paths

CONCLUSIONS

A method of analysing the post-failure behavior of laminated composite has been given. The method has been shown for the sample problem; a cross-ply composite of Tsai which is subjected to uniaxial tension. When the ductile material is assumed, the results almost coincide with that of Tsai. However, microscopically, the stress-strain diagram immediately after the knee-point takes a staggered path. In addition to $F_{Tz}^{(2)}$ failure of Tsai, $F_{Tz}^{(1)}$ failure occurs in the outer layer. When the brittle material is assumed, the stress-strain diagram differs significantly from that of Tsai. A notable slip occurs immediately after the knee-point. The unloading case has been explained, too. The unloading path is parallel to the elastic path in the stress-strain diagram.

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